

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R K	K E L	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Cyclosa camelodes</i> (Thorell, 1878)	/	/																	133, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa confraga</i> (Thorell, 1892)	/	/													/				133, 93, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa cucurbitoria</i> (Yin et al., 1990)	/	/				/													140, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa dives</i> Simon, 1877	/	/					/		/										140, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	/	/	/		/		/	/			/								213 (as <i>Epeira anseripes</i>), 214, 148, 141, 93, 199, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa mulmeinensis</i> (Thorell, 1887)	/	/	/		/										/				93, 42, 197, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa nigra</i> Yin et al., 1990	/	/										/							138, 146,233
<i>Cyclosa paupercula</i> Simon, 1893	/		/	/															95, 146,233
<i>Cyphalonotus selangor</i> Dzulhelmi, 2014	/	/						/											140, 93, 146,233
<i>Cyrtarachne conica</i> (O. Pickard Cambridge, 1901	/																		148, 146,233
<i>Cyrtarachne keralensis</i> Jose 2011	/	/						/											138, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora beccarii</i> (Thorell, 1878)	/		/		/														93, 197, 93, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora cicatrosa</i> (Stoliczka 1869)	/	/						/											214, 95, 93, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora cylindroides</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	/	/	/	/	/		/				/								138, 143, 136, 93, 170, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora eczematica</i> (Thorell, 1892)	/	/																	133, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora exanthematica</i> (Doleschall 1859)	/		/	/															95, 93, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora hainanensis</i> Yin et al. 1990	/	/					/	/											214, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora moluccensis</i> (Doleschall, 1857)	/	/	/	/	/		/	/			/								197, 214, 148, 143, 136, 200, 93, 170, 146,233
<i>Cyrtophora unicolor</i> (Doleschall 1857)	/		/	/	/														95, 93, 146,233
<i>Deione lingulata</i> Han, Zhu & Levi 2009	/		/	/	/														95, 93, 146,233

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<i>Neoscona inusta</i> (L. Koch, 1871)	/	/	/	/	/							/							140, 143 (all as <i>Araneus inustus</i>), 146,233
<i>Neoscona nautica</i> (Koch 1875)	/	/	/	/	/					/	/								42, 246, 143, 136, 169, 146,233
<i>Neoscona punctigera</i> (Doleschall 1857)	/	/	/	/	/		/												138, 42, 146,233
<i>Neoscona rumpfi</i> (Thorell 1887)	/	/										/							8, 138, 146,233
<i>Neoscona theisi</i> Walckenaer 1841	/	/	/	/	/							/							138, 143, 93, 146,233
<i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall 1865)	/	/	/	/	/		/												193 (as <i>Araneus decens</i>),246, 143, 146, 170,233
<i>Nephila kuhli</i> Doleschall 1859	/	/																	133, 146,233
<i>Nephila pilipes</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	/	/	/	/	/			/		/	/								141, 169, 174, 131, 146,233
<i>Nephilengys malabarensis</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	/	/	/	/	/			/		/	/								41 (also as <i>Nephilengys niahensis</i>), 213, 8, 146, 214, 133, 197, 95, 93, 131,233
<i>Ordgarius sexspinosus</i> (Thorell, 1894)	/		/	/															93, 146,233
<i>Parawixia dehaani</i> (Doleschall 1859)	/	/	/	/	/		/	/			/								190 (as <i>Araneus dehaani</i>), 146, 147, 25, 26, 143, 136, 93, 199,233
<i>Parawixia hypocrita</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)	/	/					/												27,233
<i>Perilla teres</i> Thorell, 1895	/	/							/										102, 146,233
<i>Pitharatus junghuhi</i> (Doleschall, 1859)	/																		190, 146,233
<i>Polys apiculatus</i> Thorell, 1898	/	/																	133, 146,233
<i>Polys dubius</i> (Walckenaer, 1842)	/	/																	133, 146,233
<i>Polys elevatus</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/					/				/								170,233
<i>Polys idae</i> (Ausserer, 1871)	/	/	/	/	/		/				/								93, 146,233
<i>Polys illepidus</i> C. L. Koch, 1843	/	/	/	/	/			/			/								188, 147, 133, 197, 95, 93, 146,233
<i>Polys stygius</i> Thorell, 1898	/	/	/	/	/						/								93, 146,233
<i>Porcataraneus bengalensis</i> (Tikader, 1975)	/	/					/												140 (as <i>Chorizopes bengalensis</i>),233

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<i>Singa perpolita</i> (Thorell 1892)	/	/	/	/					/	/									95, 138, 93, 146,233
<i>Talhybia depressa</i> Thorell, 1898	/		/	/															93, 146,233
<i>Thelacantha brevispina</i> (Doleschall, 1857)	/	/						/	/	/									213 (as <i>Gasteracantha brevispina</i>), 133, 146, 197, 214, 202, 93,233
<i>Thelacantha cuspidata</i> (C. L. Koch, 1837)	/	/																	133 (as <i>Gastheracantha cuspidata</i>),233
<i>Trichonephila antipodiana</i> (Walckenaer 1841)	/	/					*			/								/	247, 248, 93, 146, (all as <i>Nephila antipodiana</i>),233
<i>Zygiella calyptrata</i> (Workman, 1894)	/	/	/	/	/			/							/				214, 133, 143, 136, 93, 146,233
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<i>Idioctis littoralis</i> Abraham, 1924	/	/													/				133, 146, 148,233
<i>Monodontium sarawak</i> (Raven 2008)	/		/	/															95, 146,233
<i>Rhianodes atratus</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/								/									213 (as <i>Rhianus atratus</i>), 133, 148, 146, 93,233
<i>Sason sundaicum</i> Schwendinger 2003	/	/																	178, 146,233
<i>Sipalolasma aedificatrix</i> Abraham, 1924	/	/															/		2, 133, 148, 146,233
<i>Sipalolasma ophiriensis</i> Abraham, 1924	/	/															/		2, 133, 148, 146,233
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<i>Damarchus cavernicola</i> Abraham, 1924	/	/						/											133 (as <i>Latouchia batuensis</i>), 148 (as <i>Nemesiidae</i>), 2, 132, 146,233
<i>Damarchus montanus</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/																	133, 146,233
<i>Damarchus workmani</i> Thorell, 1891	/	/				/				/									133, 146,233
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<i>Cheiracanthium turiae</i> Strand 1917	/		/	/															95, 146,233
<i>Eutittha insulana</i> (Thorell 1878)	/	/																	46 (as <i>Cheiracanthium insulanum</i>),233
Cithaeronidae																			

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<i>Cithaeron praedonius</i> Cambridge 1872	/	/																158, 146,233
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<i>Clubiona apiculata</i> Dankittipakul & Singtripop, 2014	/		/		/													34, 146,233
<i>Clubiona biembolata</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 93, 146,233
<i>Clubiona concinna</i> (Thorell 1887)	/	/																133, 146,233
<i>Clubiona conica</i> Dankittipakul & Singtripop, 2014	/		/		/													34, 146,233
<i>Clubiona cylindriformis</i> Dankittipakul & Singtripop, 2014	/		/	/														34, 146,233
<i>Clubiona damirkovaci</i> Deeleman- Reinhold, 2001	/	/						/										46, 87, 146,233
<i>Clubiona inquilina</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46, 146,233
<i>Clubiona krisisensis</i> Barrion & Litsinger 1995	/	/	/		/		/			/								140, 46, 146,233
<i>Clubiona meraukensis</i> Chrysanthus 1967	/	/					/											149, 146,233
<i>Clubiona pahilistapyasea</i> Barrion & Litsinger, 1995	/		/		/													46, 146,233
<i>Clubiona parconcinna</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95,233
<i>Clubiona scandens</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46, 146,233
<i>Clubiona silvestris</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 146,233
<i>Malamatidia bohorokensis</i> Deeleman-Reinhold 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 146,233
<i>Malamatidia vethi</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46, 146,233
<i>Matidia trinotata</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/								213, 133, 146, 197,233
<i>Nusatidia aeria</i> (Simon, 1897)	/	/	/		/													133, 146, 46,233

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<i>Nusatidia borneensis</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 93, 146,233
<i>Nusatidia javana</i> Simon 1896	/	/																46, 146,233
<i>Nusatidia melanobursa</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													93, 146,233
<i>Pristidia longistila</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 93, 146,233
<i>Pristidia prima</i> Deeleman- Reinhold, 2001	/	/	/		/													46, 146,233
<i>Pristidia viridissima</i> Deeleman-Reinhold 2001	/	/	/	/	/		/			/								46, 96, 95, 93,146,233
<i>Pteroneta saltans</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46,146,233
<i>Pteroneta tertia</i> Deeleman- Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 93,146,233
<i>Scopalio verrens</i> Deeleman- Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46,146,233
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<i>Aetius bicuspidatus</i> Yamasaki, 2020	/		/	/														243,,233
<i>Aetius decollatus</i> O.P.- Cambridge 1896	/	/						/										138,146,233
<i>Aetius nocturnus</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46,146,233
<i>Allomedmassa deelemanae</i> Dankittipakul & Singtripop, 2014	/		/		/													37, 93,146,233
<i>Aochinomma nitidum</i> (Thorell 1895)	/	/								/								140,146,233
<i>Castianeira zetes</i> (Simon 1897)	/	/						/										140,233
<i>Castoponera christae</i> Yamasaki, 2016	/		/	/														239,233
<i>Castoponera ciliata</i> (Deeleman- Reinhold, 1993)	/	/					/											43, 133,146,233
<i>Castoponera lecythus</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 95, 93,146,233

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<i>Urozelotes rusticus</i> (Koch 1872)	/		/	/														41, 133, 95,146, 233
<i>Wydundra voc</i> (Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001)	/	/																46 (as <i>Molycrria voc</i>),146,233
<i>Zelotes sarawakensis</i> (Thorell 1890)	/		/	/	/													216 (as <i>Prothesima sarawakensis</i>), (95, 46,146,233
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<i>Alistra</i> sp.	/	/																233
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<i>Hersilia jajaj</i> Rheims & Brescovit, 2004	/		/		/													171,146,233
<i>Hersilia kerekot</i> Rheims & Brescovit, 2004	/		/		/													171,146,233
<i>Hersilia kinabaluensis</i> M. Baehr & B. Baehr, 1993	/		/		/													7,146,233
<i>Hersilia lelabah</i> Rheims & Brescovit, 2004	/		/		/													171, 93,146,233
<i>Hersilia sumatrana</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/	/	/						/								133, 95,146,233
<i>Tamopsis floreni</i> Rheims & Brescovit, 2004	/		/		/													171,146,233
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<i>Aperturina paniculus</i> Tanasevitch, 2014	/	/					/			/							/	204, 210,233
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<i>Asiafroneta pallida</i> Tanasevitch 2020	/		/	/	/													208,146,233
<i>Bathyphantes paracymbialis</i> Tanasevitch, 2014	/	/					/		/									204,146,233
<i>Batueta baculum</i> Tanasevitch, 2014	/	/	/	/		/				/								204, 210,233
<i>Batueta voluta</i> Locket, 1982	/	/				/										/		112, 129, 204,146,233
<i>Ceratinopsis blesti</i> Locket, 1982	/	/						/										133, 129,146,233
<i>Ceratinopsis orientalis</i> Locket, 1982	/	/				/												112, 133,146,233

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<i>Dubiaranea deelemanae</i> Millidge, 1995	/		/		/														130,146,233
<i>Enguterothrix simpulum</i> (Tanasevitch, 2014)	/		/		/														205,146,233
<i>Erigone bifurca</i> Locket, 1982	/	/					/												112, 129, 8, 205,146,233
<i>Erigone prominens</i> Bösenberg & Strand, 1906	/	/															/		206,146,233
<i>Gongylidioides pectinatus</i> Tanasevitch, 2011	/	/										/							204,,233
<i>Indophantes kalimantanus</i> Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 2003	/		/		/														173,146,233
<i>Indophantes kinabalu</i> Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 2003	/		/		/														173,146,233
<i>Indophantes lehtineni</i> Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 2003	/		/		/														173,146,233
<i>Johorea decorata</i> Locket, 1982	/	/													/				112, 129,146,233
<i>Johorea pectinata</i> Tanasevitch, 2022	/						/												210,233
<i>Kalimagone cuspidata</i> Tanasevitch, 2017	/		/		/														206, 210,233
<i>Kalimagone rotunda</i> Tanasevitch, 2017	/		/		/														206,,233
<i>Kenocymbium deelemanae</i> Millidge & Russell-Smith, 1992	/	/					/												205, 129,146, 210,233
<i>Knischatiria tuberosa</i> Wunderlich, 1995	/	/					/												133,146,233
<i>Locketina murphyorum</i> Tanasevitch, 2022	/		/		/														210,233
<i>Locketina versa</i> Locket, 1982	/	/					/												112, 129, 133 (all as <i>Kuala versa</i>),146, 210,233
<i>Microbathyphantes minimus</i> (Locket, 1982)	/	/					/												112, 129, 132, 146 (all as <i>Kaestneria minima</i>) 210,233
<i>Nasoona asocialis</i> (Wunderlich, 1974)	/	/					/												204,146, 210,233

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	A	M	O	W	B	A	H	E	D	E	N	R	E	U	O	E	E	E	
	L		R	K	H	B	G	L	H	R	G	K	L	L	H	L	G	R	
<i>Nasoona chrysanthusi</i> Locket, 1982	/	/					/		/			/	/		/				112, 129, 133, 204, 93,146, 210,233
<i>Nasoona crucifera</i> (Thorell, 1895)	/	/	/	/			/						/						112, 129, 133 (all as <i>Nasoona prominula</i>), 204, 208,146, 210,233
<i>Nematogmus dentimanus</i> Simon, 1886	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Nerienne beccarii</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/		/		/														42,,233
<i>Nerienne macella</i> (Thorell, 1898)	/	/	/	/	/		/	/				/							112, 133, 204, 93,146, 210,233
<i>Nerienne strandia</i> (Blauvelt, 1936)	/		/	/															95,146,233
<i>Nerienne sundaica</i> (Simon, 1905)	/		/																146,233
<i>Oedothorax bifoveatus</i> Tanasevitch, 2017	/		/		/														206, 233
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879)	/		/		/														205,146,233
<i>Pahangone mirabilis</i> Tanasevitch, 2018	/	/					/												207, 210,233
<i>Parameioneta spicata</i> Locket, 1982	/	/					/	/											112, 129, 133, 204,146, 210,233
<i>Plectembolus quadriflectus</i> Millidge & Russell-Smith, 1992	/	/	/				/						/						146,233
<i>Plectembolus</i> <i>quinquefectus</i> Millidge & Russell-Smith, 1992	/	/					/		/										129, 96, 204, 205,146,233
<i>Plectembolus triflectus</i> Millidge R-Smith, 1992	/	/												/					133, 129, 210,233
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<i>Prosoponoides sinense</i> (Chen, 1991)	/	/					/												210,233
<i>Pseudomicrocentria uncata</i> Tanasevitch, 2020	/		/		/														209,,233
<i>Tapinopa undata</i> Zhao & Li, 2014	/	/					/												210,233
<i>Tapinopa vara</i> Locket, 1982	/	/					/												112, 129, 133, 204, 233

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<i>Sphingius superbus</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2011	/	/																	35,146,233
<i>Sphingius thecatus</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/									213, 133,146,233
<i>Sphingius vivax</i> (Thorell 1897)	/	/					/												46,146,233
<i>Teutamus andrewdavisii</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/														46,146,233
<i>Teutamus apiculatus</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/					/												36,,233
<i>Teutamus brachiatus</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Teutamus calceolatus</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/															/		33,146,233
<i>Teutamus deelemanae</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/													/				33,146,233
<i>Teutamus globularis</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Teutamus leptothecus</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/													/				33,146,233
<i>Teutamus lioneli</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Teutamus politus</i> (Thorell 1890)	/	/							/		/								213, 46 ,146,233
<i>Teutamus rama</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/																	33,146,233
<i>Teutamus seculatus</i> Dankittipakul, Tavano & Singtripop 2012	/	/													/				33,146,233

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<i>Liphistius tempurung</i> (Platnick, 1997)	/	/										/							179, 159,146,233
<i>Liphistius tioman</i> Platnick & Sedgwick, 1984	/	/				/													133, 181,146,233
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<i>Artoria weiweii</i> Wang, Zhang and Peng 2019	/		/		/														219,146,233
<i>Draposa tenasserimensis</i> (Thorell 1895)	/	/																	101,146,233
<i>Draposa zhanjiangensis</i> (Yin et al. 1995)	/	/	/	/			/												148 (as <i>Pardosa zhanjiangensis</i>), 101, 95,146,233
<i>Hippasa holmerae</i> Thorell 1895	/	/	/		/					/					/				133, 141, 93,146,233
<i>Lysania pygmaea</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/									213, 133,146,233
<i>Lysania sabahensis</i> Lehtinen & Hippa, 1979	/		/		/														105,146,233
<i>Pardosa apostoli</i> Barrion & Litsinger 1995	/	/																	104,146,233
<i>Pardosa birmanica</i> Simon, 1884	/		/		/														141,146,233
<i>Pardosa caliraya</i> Barrion & Litsinger, 1995	/	/							/										174, 233
<i>Pardosa heterophthalmus</i> (Simon, 1898)	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Pardosa irretita</i> Simon, 1886	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Pardosa laidlawi</i> Simon, 1901	/	/								/									133,146,233
<i>Pardosa milvina</i> (Hentz, 1844)	/	/				/													25, 233
<i>Pardosa pinangensis</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/									/								213 (as <i>Lycosa pinangensis</i>), 133,146,233
<i>Pardosa pseudoannulata</i> (Bosenberg & Strand 1906)	/	/	/		/		/												244, 8, 143, 93, 199,146,233

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<i>Pardosa pusiola</i> (Thorell, 1891)	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	213 (as <i>Lycosa pusiola</i>), 42, 133, 95, 143, 93, 170,146,233
<i>Pardosa rabulana</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/																133,146,233
<i>Pardosa semicana</i> Simon 1885	/	/													/			187, 133,146,233
<i>Pardosa sumatrana</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/	/		/													148, 93,146,233
<i>Passiena spinicrus</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/	/		/					/								213, 133, 203,146,233
<i>Trochosa aquatica</i> Tanaka, 1985	/		/		/													93,146,233
<i>Venonia coruscans</i> (Thorell 1894)	/	/	/		/		/			/								133, 26, 25, 93,146,233
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<i>Tamin simoni</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/														95,146,233
<i>Xantharia floreni</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/		/													46,146,233
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<i>Nesticella connectens</i> Wunderlich, 1995	/	/					/											133,146,233
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<i>Gamasomorpha ophiria</i> Eichenberger 2012	/	/																57,146,233
<i>Gamasomorpha petoteca</i> Eichenberger 2012	/	/																57,146,233
<i>Gamasomorpha raya</i> Eichenberger 2012	/	/																57,146,233
<i>Gamasomorpha schmilingi</i> Eichenberger 2012	/	/																57,146,233
<i>Gamasomorpha squalens</i> Eichenberger 2012	/	/																57,146,233
<i>Ischnothyreus florifer</i> Kranz-Baltensperger 2011	/		/	/														98, 95,146,233
<i>Ischnothyreus matang</i> Kranz-Baltensperger 2011	/		/	/														98, 95,146,233
<i>Ischnothyreus mulumi</i> Kranz-Baltensperger 2011	/		/	/														95,146,233
<i>Ischnothyreus namo</i> Kranz- Baltensperger 2012	/	/				/												99,146,233
<i>Ischnothyreus peltifer</i> (Simon, 1892)	/		/		/													42,,233
<i>Ischnothyreus serapi</i> Kranz- Baltensperger 2011	/		/	/														98, 95,146,233
<i>Ischnothyreus tekek</i> Kranz- Baltensperger 2012	/	/				/												99,146,233
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<i>Prethopalpus brunei</i> Baehr 2012	/		/	/														6, 95,146,233
<i>Prethopalpus deelemanae</i> Baehr & Thoma 2012	/		/	/														6, 95,146,233
<i>Prethopalpus kropfi</i> Baehr 2012	/		/	/														6, 95,146,233
<i>Prethopalpus sabah</i> Baehr, 2012	/		/		/													6,146,233
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<i>Sicariomorpha maschwitzi</i> (Wunderlich, 1995)	/	/											/					234, 133, (both as <i>Gamasomorpha maschwitzi</i>),146,233

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<i>Belisana floreni</i> Huber, 2005	/		/		/													68,146,233
<i>Belisana fraser</i> Huber, 2005	/	/					/											68, 148,146,233
<i>Belisana kinabalu</i> Huber 2005	/		/		/													68,146,233
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<i>Belisana nomis</i> Huber, 2005	/	/													/			68, 148,146,233
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<i>Calapnita bario</i> Huber, 2017	/		/	/														71, 93,146,233
<i>Calapnita magaseng</i> Huber, 2017	/		/	/														71,146,233
<i>Calapnita saluang</i> Huber, 2011	/	/					/	/		/		/			/			71,146,233
<i>Cantikus erawan</i> (Huber, 2011)	/	/					/											76 (as <i>Pholcus erawan</i>),146,233
<i>Cantikus halabala</i> (Huber, 2011)	/	/					/	/	/		/				/			76 (as <i>Pholcus halabala</i>),,233
<i>Cantikus lintang</i> (Huber, 2016)	/		/	/														73 (as <i>Pholcus lintang</i>),,233
<i>Cantikus sabah</i> (Huber, 2011)	/		/		/													69 (as <i>Pholcus sabah</i>), 93,146,233
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<i>Cantikus ubin</i> (Huber, 2016)	/		/		/													70 (as <i>Pholcus ubin</i>), 93,146,233
<i>Crossopriza iyoni</i> (Blackwall 1867)	/	/	/		/					/	/							96, 141, 93, 169 ,146,233
<i>Hantu kapit</i> Huber, 2016	/		/	/														70,146,233
<i>Hantu niah</i> Huber, 2016	/		/	/														70,146,233
<i>Holocneminus multiguttatus</i> (Simon, 1905)	/	/	/		/													44, 133,146,233

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<i>Kelabita andulau</i> (Huber, 2011)	/		/	/															69, 95, 70 (all as <i>Pholcus andulau</i>), 93,146,233
<i>Kelabita lambir</i> (Huber, 2016)	/		/	/															70 (as <i>Pholcus lambir</i>),,233
<i>Kintaqa satun</i> (Huber, 2011)	/	/							/										73 (as <i>Pholcus satun</i>),146,233
<i>Leptopholcus borneensis</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 1986	/		/		/														69,,233
<i>Meraha kinabalu</i> (Huber, 2011)	/		/		/														69 (as <i>Pholcus kinabalu</i>),146,233
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<i>Nipisa anai</i> (Huber, 2017)	/	/					/												71,146,233
<i>Nipisa bankirai</i> (Huber, 2017)	/		/	/															71,146,233
<i>Nipisa bidayuh</i> (Huber 2017)	/		/	/															71 as <i>Calapnita bidayuh</i> ,146,233
<i>Nipisa deelemanae</i> Huber, 2011	/		/		/														71 as <i>Calapnita deelemanae</i> ,146,233
<i>Nipisa kubah</i> (Huber 2017)	/		/	/															71 as <i>Calapnita kubah</i> ,146,233
<i>Nipisa lehi</i> (Huber 2017)	/		/	/															71 as <i>Calapnita lehi</i> ,146,233
<i>Nipisa phasmoides</i> (Deeleman-Reinhold, 1986)	/		/		/														42 (as <i>Calapnita phasmoides</i>),,233
<i>Nipisa phyllicola</i> Deeleman- Reinhold, 1986	/	/	/	/			/	/			/	/			/				39, 133, 95, 69, 71 (all as <i>Calapnita phyllicola</i>), 93,146,233
<i>Nipisa semengoh</i> Huber 2011	/		/	/															95, 69, 71 (all as <i>Calapnita semengoh</i>),146,233
<i>Pholcus ceylonicus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869	/	/					/												69,,233
<i>Pholcus gracillimus</i> Thorell 1890	/	/									/								69, 138,146,233
<i>Pholcus kohi</i> Huber, 2011	/	/					/							/					69,146,233
<i>Pholcus negara</i> Huber, 2011	/		/		/														93,146,233
<i>Pholcus phalangioides</i> (Fuesslin 1775)	/	/																	8,146,233
<i>Physocyclus globosus</i> (Taczanowski, 1874)	/	/	/		/						/								133, 143,146,233

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<i>Pribumia atrigularis</i> (Simon, 1901)	/	/					/	/							/				133, 197 (both as <i>Uthina atrigularis</i>), 69, 72 (both as <i>Pholcus atrigularis</i>), 170,146,233
<i>Pribumia diopsis</i> Simon, 1901	/																		69 (as <i>Pholcus diopsis</i>),,233
<i>Savarna miser</i> Bristowe, 1952	/	/	/		/			/											22, 133, 132, 42 (all as <i>Spermophora miser</i>),,233
<i>Smeringopus pallidus</i> (Blackwall 1858)	/	/	/		/			/											42, 147, 148 ,,233
<i>Tissahamia gombak</i> (Huber, 2011)	/	/						/											69 (as <i>Pholcus gombak</i>),146,233
<i>Tissahamia ledang</i> (Huber, 2011)	/	/													/				73 (as <i>Pholcus ledang</i>),146,233
<i>Tissahamia tanahrata</i> (Huber, 2016)	/	/					/												73 (as <i>Pholcus tanahrata</i>),,233
<i>Tissahamia uludong</i> (Huber, 2016)	/	/					/												73 (as <i>Pholcus uludong</i>),,233
<i>Tissahamia vescula</i> (Simon, 1901)	/	/										/							69 (as <i>Pholcus vesculus</i>),146,233
<i>Uthina luzonica</i> Simon 1893	/	/					/				/				/				133, 69, 93,146,233
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<i>Vytfutia pallens</i> Deeleman-Reinhold 1989	/		/	/															41, 95,146,233
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<i>Dendrolycosa fusca</i> Doleschall, 1859	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Dendrolycosa lepida</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/		/		/														94,146,233
<i>Dolomedes femoralis</i> Hasselt, 1882	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Dolomedes mizhoanus</i> Kishida 1936	/	/				/				/									149,146,233
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<i>Althepus spiralis</i> Li, Li & Jager 2014	/	/					/											110,146,233
<i>Leclercera ocellata</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 1995	/		/		/													45,146,233
<i>Merizocera crinita</i> (Fage, 1929)	/	/						/										60, 22 (both as <i>Psiloderces crinitus</i>), 133, 132,146,233
<i>Psiloderces althepoides</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 1995	/		/		/													44,146,233
<i>Psiloderces enigmatus</i> Deeleman-Reinhold 1995	/		/	/														95,146,233
<i>Psiloderces pulcher</i> Deeleman-Reinhold 1995	/		/	/														95,146,233
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<i>Agorius constrictus</i> Simon, 1901	/	/					/											133, 197, 165, 25,146,233
<i>Agorius gracilipes</i> Thorell, 1877	/	/																133,146,233
<i>Agorius hyodoi</i> Yamasaki, 2020	/		/	/														242,,233
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<i>Anarrhotus fossulatus</i> Simon, 1902	/	/	/	/														133, 197, 95,146,233
<i>Artabrus erythrocephalus</i> (Koch 1846)	/	/																133,146,233
<i>Asemonea pinangensis</i> Wanless, 1980	/	/									/							221, 133, 197,146,233
<i>Augustaea formicaria</i> Szombathy, 1915	/	/																133,146,233
<i>Bathippus morsitans</i> Pocock 1897	/		/	/														161, 95,146,233
<i>Bathippus pahang</i> (Zhang, Song & Li 2003)	/	/					/											259,146,233
<i>Bathippus schalleri</i> Simon 1902	/	/									/							192, 133,146,233
<i>Bavia aericeps</i> Simon, 1877	/	/																133, 197, ,146,233

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<i>Bavia nessagyna</i> Maddison, 2020	/		/	/														121,146,233
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<i>Bianor diversipes</i> Simon 1901	/	/										/						133, ,146,233
<i>Bocus angusticollis</i> Deeleman-Reinhold & Floren, 2003	/		/		/													49, 94,146,233
<i>Bristowia heterospinosa</i> Reimoser, 1934	/	/																133, 197,146,233
<i>Burmattus pococki</i> (Thorell 1895)	/	/	/	/	/		/			/								138, 141, 94, 199,146,233
<i>Canama forceps</i> (Doleschall, 1859)	/	/																133,146,233
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<i>Carrhotus malayanus</i> Proszynski 1992	/	/											/					163, 133, ,146,233
<i>Carrhotus olivaceus</i> (Peckham & Peckham 1907)	/		/	/														154, 95,146,233
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<i>Colyttus bilineatus</i> Thorell, 1891	/	/	/	/						/								213, 133, 94,146,233
<i>Colyttus robustus</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2012	/	/					/											257,146,233
<i>Colyttus striatus</i> (Simon, 1902)	/		/	/	/													168, 95 (both as <i>Donoessus striatus</i>), 94,146,233
<i>Copocrossa politiventris</i> Simon, 1901	/	/									/							191, 133, ,146,233
<i>Cosmophasis lami</i> Berry, Beatty & Prószyński, 1997	/		/		/													94,146,233
<i>Cosmophasis thalassina</i> (C. L. Koch,1846)	/	/	/		/													133, 197, 141, 136 (both as <i>Cosmophasis umbratica</i>),146,233
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<i>Cytaea oreophila</i> Simon 1902	/	/					/	/										138, 170,146,233
<i>Cytaea semongohi</i> Prószyński & Deeleman-Reinhold 2013	/		/	/														168, 95,146,233
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<i>Echeclus concinnus</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/								213, 133, ,146,233
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<i>Myrmarachne kochi</i> Reimoser, 1925	/																	186 (as <i>Salticus melanocephalus</i>),146,233
<i>Myrmarachne lagarosoma</i> Yamasaki, 2018	/		/	/														240,,233
<i>Myrmarachne lambirensis</i> Yamasaki & Ahmad, 2013	/		/	/	/													238,146,233
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<i>Myrmarachne manducator</i> (Westwood, 1841)	/																	197,146,233
<i>Myrmarachne markaha</i> Barrion & Litsinger, 1995	/		/		/													238,146,233
<i>Myrmarachne melanocephala</i> MacLeay, 1839	/		/		/						/							238, 94,146,233
<i>Myrmarachne nitidissima</i> (Thorell, 1877)	/		/		/													238,146,233
<i>Myrmarachne opaca</i> (Karsch, 1880)	/	/	/	/	/		/											238, 94,146,233
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<i>Neobrettus tibialis</i> (Prószyński, 1978)	/	/	/		/		/							/				224, 94,146,233

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<i>Parabathippus kiabau</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2012	/		/		/														257,146,233
<i>Parabathippus macilentus</i> Thorell 1890	/	/						/											138,146,233
<i>Parabathippus magnus</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2012	/	/					/												257,146,233
<i>Parabathippus petrae</i> (Proszynski and Deeleman-Reinhold 2012)	/		/		/														138, 143,146,233
<i>Parabathippus sedatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham 1907)	/		/	/															154, 95,146,233
<i>Parabathippus shelfordi</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1907)	/		/	/	/														154 (as <i>Bathippus shelfordii</i>), 94,146,233
<i>Paracyrba wanlessi</i> Zabka & Kovac, 1996	/	/						/											253, 133,146,233
<i>Pengmarengo chelifera</i> (Simon, 1900)	/		/		/														12,,233
<i>Phaecius malayensis</i> Wanless, 1981	/	/	/	/	/														223, 133, 197, 141, 136, 94,146,233
<i>Phaecius alabangensis</i> Wijeshinghe 1991	/		/	/															95,,233
<i>Phidippus audax</i> (Hentz, 1845)	/	/									/								213 (as <i>Megatimus severus</i>), 133 (as <i>Phidippus severus</i>),,233
<i>Philates szutsi</i> Benjamin, 2004	/		/		/														12,,233
<i>Philates thaleri</i> Benjamin, 2004	/		/		/														12,,233
<i>Phintella bifurcilinea</i> (Bosenberg and Strand 1906)	/		/		/			/											140, 94,146,233
<i>Phintella debilis</i> (Thorell 1891)	/	/	/	/	/			/		/									213 (as <i>Chrysilla debilis</i>), 95, 140, 141, 94,146,233
<i>Phintella suavis</i> (Simon, 1885)	/	/													/				187(as <i>Thiania suavis</i>), 133,146,233
<i>Phintella vittata</i> (C. L. Koch, 1846)	/	/	/	/				/		/									213 (as <i>Maevia alternans</i>), 133, 197, 148, 95, 199, 94,146,233
<i>Phintelloides versicolor</i> (C. L. Koch, 1846)	/		/	/	/					/									194 (as <i>Chrysilla versicolor</i>), 133, 197, 95, 141, 94 (all as <i>Phintella versicolor</i>),146,233

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<i>Ptocasius weyersi</i> Simon, 1885	/	/	/	/						/					/				136, 94,146,233
<i>Pystira ephippigera</i> (Simon, 1885)	/	/	/	/	/					/									133, 94, 95 (as <i>Omoedus ephippigera</i>),146,233
<i>Rhene albigera</i> (C. L. Koch, 1848)	/	/	/		/														133, 141,146,233
<i>Rhene bufo</i> (Doleschall, 1859)	/	/																	133, ,146,233
<i>Rhene flavigera</i> (C. L. Koch, 1848)	/	/	/		/														133, 94,146,233
<i>Rhene nigrita</i> (C. L. Koch, 1846)	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Rhene rubrigera</i> (Thorell, 1887)	/	/	/		/					/									213 (as <i>Homalattus analis</i>), 133, 141,146,233
<i>Rudakius maureri</i> Proszynski, 1992	/	/						/											162, 133 (both as <i>Pseudacius maureri</i>),146,233
<i>Saaristattus tropicus</i> Logunov & Azarkina 2008	/	/							/										120,146,233
<i>Siler collingwoodi</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge 1871)	/		/	/															95,,233
<i>Siler pulcher</i> Simon, 1901	/	/											/						191, 133 ,146,233
<i>Siler semiglaucus</i> (Simon, 1901)	/	/	/		/					/									94,146,233
<i>Sobasina sylvatica</i> Edmund & Proszynski 200	/	/																	54,146,233
<i>Sparbambus gombakensis</i> (Zhang, Woon & Li	/	/						/											260,146,233
<i>Spartaeus spinimanus</i> (Thorell, 1878)	/	/	/	/				/		/									224, 133, 95, 94,146,233
<i>Spartaeus wildtracki</i> Wanless, 1987	/	/						/											225, 133 ,146,233
<i>Stagetillus opaciceps</i> Simon 1885	/	/					/	/								/			133, 94, 121,146,233
<i>Stertinius borneensis</i> Logunov, 2018	/		/		/														115,,233
<i>Taivala invisitata</i> Peckham & Peckham 1907	/		/	/															154, 95,146,233
<i>Taraxella hillyardi</i> Wanless, 1987	/	/						/											225, 133 ,146,233

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<i>Tisaniba inusitata</i> Logunov, 2020	/	/					/												118,,233
<i>Tisaniba loebli</i> Logunov, 2020	/	/					/												118,,233
<i>Tisaniba mulu</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2014	/		/	/															118,,233
<i>Tisaniba selan</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2014	/		/	/															258,,233
<i>Tisaniba tioman</i> Logunov, 2020	/	/					/												118,,233
<i>Tisanibainepta bijibijan</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2014	/		/	/															258 (as <i>Tisaniba bibijan</i>), 118,146,233
<i>Tisanibainepta kubah</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2014	/		/	/															258 (as <i>Tisaniba kubah</i>), 118,146,233
<i>Tisanibainepta pahang</i> Zhang & Maddison, 2014	/	/					/												118,146,233
<i>Tisanibainepta selasi</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2014)	/		/	/															258,146,233
<i>Toxeus cuneatus</i> (Badcock, 1918)	/	/																/	54, 133, (both as <i>Myrmarachne cuneata</i>),146,233
<i>Toxeus grossa</i> Edmunds & Prosyn'ski, 2003	/	/					/												54(as <i>Myrmarachne grossa</i>),146,233
<i>Toxeus hirsutipalpi</i> (Edmunds & Prószyński, 2003)	/																		55 (as <i>Myrmarachne hirsutipalpi</i>),146,233
<i>Toxeus maxillosus</i> C. L. Koch, 1846	/	/	/		/		/											/	94,146,233
<i>Uroballus kinabalu</i> Logunov, 2018	/		/		/														115,146,233
<i>Uroballus kaponeni</i> Logunov, 2014	/		/	/															114,,233
<i>Uroballus peckhami</i> Zabka, 1985	/	/					/												138,146,233
<i>Vailimia bakoensis</i> Proszynski & Deeleman-Reinhold 2013	/		/	/															168, 95,146,233
<i>Vailimia jianyuae</i> Proszynski & Deeleman-Reinhold 2013	/		/	/															168, 95,146,233

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<i>Vailimia masinei</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1907)	/		/	/															168,,233
<i>Viciria arrogans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1907	/		/	/															154,,233
<i>Viciria concolor</i> Peckham & Peckham 1907	/		/	/															154, 95,,233
<i>Viciria lucida</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1907	/		/	/															154,,233
<i>Viciria miranda</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1907	/		/	/															154,,233
<i>Viciria moesta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1907	/		/	/															154,,233
<i>Viciria paludosa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1907	/		/	/															154,,233
<i>Viciria pavesii</i> Thorell 1877	/	/								/									95, 138, 143, 94 (all as <i>Viciria praemandibularis</i>), 123,146,233
<i>Viciria petulans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1907	/		/	/															154,146,233
<i>Wanlessia sedwicki</i> Wijesinghe 1992	/		/	/															231, 95,146,233
Scytodidae																			
<i>Dictis striatipes</i> Koch, 1872	/	/																	133 (as <i>Scytodes lugubris</i>),146,233
<i>Scyloxes magna</i> Bristowe, 1952	/	/							/										22, 132 (both as <i>Scytodes magna</i>), 133, ,146,233
<i>Scytodes cavernarum</i> Roewer, 1962	/	/							/										172, 133, 132,146,233
<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer, 1837	/	/	/	/	/			/	/										143, 132,146,233
<i>Scytodes pallida</i> (Doleschall, 1859)	/	/	/	/			/	/			/								42, 147, 133, 95, 199,146,233
<i>Scytodes thoracica</i> (Latreille 1802)	/	/																	8,146,233
<i>Stedocys leopoldi</i> (Giltay, 1935)	/	/					/												103, 133, ,146,233
Selenopidae																			
<i>Siamspinops aculeatus</i> Simon, 1901	/	/								/									191 (as <i>Selenops aculeatus</i>), 133, ,146,233

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<i>Siamspinops spinescens</i> Dankittipakul & Corronca, 2009	/	/										/							30,,233
Sparassidae																			
<i>Borniella parva</i> Grall & Jäger, 2022	/		/	/															63,146,233
<i>Gnathopalystes crucifer</i> (Simon, 1880)	/	/																	133, ,146,233
<i>Gnathopalystes kochi</i> (Simon 1899)	/	/	/		/		/												133, 197, 96, 141, 94 170,146,233
<i>Heteropoda belua</i> Jager 2005	/		/	/															83, 95,146,233
<i>Heteropoda boiei</i> (Doleschall, 1859)	/	/	/	/		/	/			/			/						85, 95, 94,146,233
<i>Heteropoda borneensis</i> (Thorell 1892)	/		/	/															95,146,233
<i>Heteropoda christae</i> Jäger, 2008	/	/														/			85,146,233
<i>Heteropoda davidbowie</i> Jager 2008	/	/	/	/	/		/			/									85, 96, 141, 94,146,233
<i>Heteropoda furva</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/									213, 133, ,146,233
<i>Heteropoda garciai</i> Barrion & Litsinger 1995	/	/																	104,146,233
<i>Heteropoda hosei</i> Pocock 1897	/		/	/															161, 84, 95,146,233
<i>Heteropoda imbecilla</i> Thorell, 1892	/																		133,146,233
<i>Heteropoda javana</i> (Simon, 1880)	/	/					/												85,146,233
<i>Heteropoda leprosa</i> Simon, 1884	/																		133,146,233
<i>Heteropoda loderstaedti</i> Jäger, 2008	/	/					/												85,146,233
<i>Heteropoda lunula</i> (Doleschall, 1857)	/	/	/		/							/							78, 94,146,233
<i>Heteropoda murina</i> (Pocock 1897)	/		/	/															81, 95,146,233
<i>Heteropoda natans</i> Jager, 2005	/		/	/	/														84, 136, 94,146,233

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<i>Heteropoda nebulosa</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/									213, 133, ,146,233
<i>Heteropoda ninahagen</i> Jäger, 2008	/	/								/									85,146,233
<i>Heteropoda obtusa</i> Thorell, 1890	/		/	/															214,146,233
<i>Heteropoda parva</i> Jager, 2000	/	/										/							85,146,233
<i>Heteropoda sexpunctata</i> Simon, 1885	/	/														/			187, 133,146,233
<i>Heteropoda tetrica</i> Thorell 1897	/	/	/	/	/			/											96, 141, 94,146,233
<i>Heteropoda venatoria</i> (Linnaeus 1767)	/	/	/	/	/			/		/						/			213, 95, 140, 141, 170,146,233
<i>Menarik kecil</i> Grall & Jäger, 2022	/		/	/															63,146,233
<i>Olios mahabangkawitus</i> Barrion & Litsinger 1995	/	/																	104,146,233
<i>Pandercetes malleator</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/					/			/									213, 133. 170,146,233
<i>Rhitymna gerdmangel</i> Jäger, 2019	/	/						/											88,146,233
<i>Rhitymna pinangensis</i> (Thorell, 1891)	/	/	/	/	/			/		/									213 (as <i>Sarotes pinangensis</i>), 133, 82, 95, 94, 88,146,233
<i>Rhitymna simplex</i> Jäger, 2003	/		/		/														88,146,233
<i>Rhitymna xanthopus</i> Simon, 1901	/	/											/						133, 82, ,146,233
<i>Sinopoda forcipata</i> (Karsch 1881)	/	/																	80,146,233
<i>Sinopoda microphthalmus</i> (Fage, 1929)	/	/						/											60, 22 (both as <i>Panaretidius microphthalmus</i>), 133, 132,146,233
<i>Spariolenus tigris</i> Simon, 1880	/	/																	133, 148,146,233
<i>Thelcticopis goramensis</i> (Thorell, 1881)	/	/																	133, ,146,233
<i>Thelcticopis modesta</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/								/									213, 133, 197, ,146,233
<i>Thelcticopis orichalcea</i> (Simon, 1880)	/	/															/		145,,233

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	A	M	O	W	B	A	H	E	D	E	N	R	E	U	O	E	E	E	
	L		R	K	H	B	G	L	H	R	G	K	L	L	H	L	G	R	
<i>Thecticopis pennata</i> (Simon, 1901)	/	/											/						191 (as <i>Seramba pennata</i>), 133,146,233
<i>Tiomaniella ladam</i> Grall & Jäger, 2022	/	/				/													63,146,233
Stenochilidae																			
<i>Colopea malayana</i> Lehtinen, 1982	/	/																	107, 133, ,146,233
<i>Colopea unifoveata</i> Lehtinen, 1982	/		/		/														107,146,233
Symphytognathidae																			
<i>Anapistula jerai</i> Harvey 1998	/	/							/										64,146,233
<i>Crassignatha danaugirangensis</i> Miller et al. 2014	/		/		/														128,146,233
<i>Crassignatha haeneli</i> Wunderlich, 1995	/	/				/													235, 133,146,233
Telemidae																			
<i>Telemofila malaysiaensis</i> Wang & Li 2000	/		/	/															218, 95 (both as <i>Telema malaysiaensis</i>),146,233
Tetramblemmidae																			
<i>Ablemma circumspectans</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 1980	/		/		/														106,146,233
<i>Ablemma gombakense</i> Wunderlich, 1995	/	/							/										234, 133, ,146,233
<i>Ablemma merotai</i> Lehtinen, 1981	/		/		/														106,146,233
<i>Ablemma sedwicki</i> Shear 1978	/		/	/															184, 95,146,233
<i>Ablemma sternofoveatum</i> Lehtinen, 1981	/		/		/														106,146,233
<i>Ablemma unicolorne</i> Burger, 2008	/	/					/												24,146,233
<i>Borneomma roberti</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 1980	/		/		/														106,146,233
<i>Brignoliella besutensis</i> Lin, Li & Jager 2012	/	/															/		111,146,233

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<i>Brignoliella michaeli</i> Lehtinen, 1981	/	/									/								106, 133, ,146,233
<i>Brignoliella sarawak</i> Shear 1978	/		/	/															106, 95,146,233
<i>Brignoliella vulgaris</i> Lehtinen, 1981	/		/		/														106,146,233
<i>Pahanga centenialis</i> Lehtinen, 1981	/	/							/										106, 133, ,146,233
<i>Pahanga dura</i> Shear, 1979	/	/						/											185, 106, 133, ,146,233
<i>Sulaimania vigelandi</i> Lehtinen, 1981	/	/													/				106, 133, ,146,233
Tetragnathidae																			
<i>Dolichognatha longiceps</i> (Thorell, 1895)	/		/		/														94,,233
<i>Dyschiriognatha bedoti</i> Simon 1893	/		/	/															188, 95,146,233
<i>Leucauge argentina</i> (Hasselt, 1882)	/	/	/	/	/			/			/								213 (as <i>Argyropeira argentina</i>), 147, 133, 197, 143, 136, 174, 139.,146,233
<i>Leucauge argentina</i> <i>nigriceps</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/									/								213, 133, 197 ,146,233
<i>Leucauge celebesiana</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	/	/	/	/	/			/			/								217 (as <i>Tetrganatha celebesiana</i>), 213 (as <i>Argyropeira celebesiana</i>), 41, 133, 197, 143, 136, 94,146,233
<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	/	/	/		/			*			/								143, 94,146,233
<i>Leucauge fastigata</i> (Simon, 1877)	/	/	/		/			/			/								147, 94 (as <i>Opadometa fastigata</i>),146,233
<i>Leucauge granulata</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Leucauge grata</i> (Simon, 1877)	/	/						/			/								133, 139 (both as <i>Opadometa grata</i>),146,233
<i>Leucauge kuchingensis</i> Dzulhelmi & Suriyanti, 2015	/		/	/															139 (as <i>Opadometa kuchingensis</i>),146,233
<i>Leucauge liui</i> Zhu, Song & Zhang, 2003	/		/		/														143,146,233
<i>Leucauge quadrifasciata</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/									/								213 (as <i>Argyropeira quadrifasciata</i>), 133,146,233
<i>Leucauge sabahan</i> Dzulhelmi, 2016	/		/	/	/														143, 136, 94,146,233

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<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin 1826)	/	/																62,146,233
<i>Tetragnatha novia</i> Simon, 1901	/																	191,,233
<i>Tetragnatha pinicola</i> Koch 1870	/	/					/											138,146,233
<i>Tetragnatha praedonia</i> Koch 1878	/	/	/		/		/											140, 141,146,233
<i>Tetragnatha vermiformis</i> Emerton, 1884	/																	8,146,233
<i>Tetragnatha virescens</i> Okuma, 1979	/																	8,146,233
<i>Tylorida striata</i> (Thorell, 1877)	/	/	/	/	/		/			/								216, 213 (both as <i>Argyropeira striata</i>), 147, 95, 143, 94, 139,146,233
<i>Tylorida tianlin</i> Zhu, Song & Zhang	/	/	/		/		/											138, 143,146,233
<i>Tylorida ventralis</i> (Thorell, 1877)	/	/	/	/	/		/			/								147, 141, 136, 137, 94, 139,146, 233
Theraphosidae																		
<i>Birupes simoroxigorum</i> Gabriel & Sherwood, 2019	/		/	/														61,146, 233
<i>Chilobrachys andersoni</i> (Pocock, 1895)	/	/																133,146, 233
<i>Chilobrachys annandalei</i> Simon, 1901	/																	191,146, 233
<i>Citharognathus hosei</i> Pocock 1895	/		/	/														160, 95, 233
<i>Coremiocnemis cunicularia</i> (Simon 1892)	/	/								/								133, 228, 229,146, 233
<i>Coremiocnemis hoggi</i> West & Nunn, 2010	/	/					/											229,146,233
<i>Coremiocnemis obscura</i> West & Nunn, 2010	/	/				/					/							229, 230,146,233
<i>Coremiocnemis valida</i> Pocock 1895	/	/	/	/						/								160, 2, 133, 229, 94,146,233
<i>Cyriopagopus doriae</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/	/	/	/													155, 133, 95 (all as <i>Haplopelma doriae</i>), 94,146,233
<i>Cyriopagopus minax</i> (Thorell, 1897)	/	/																133 (as <i>Haplopelma minax</i>),146,233

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<i>Lampropelma carpenteri</i> (Smith & Jacobi, 2015)	/		/	/														196,146,233
<i>Lyrognathus robustus</i> Smith 1988	/	/				/		/			/							194, 227 (as <i>Lyrognathus liewi</i>), 133, 228,146, 233
<i>Omothymus schioedtei</i> (Thorell, 1891)	/	/									/							133 (as <i>Cyriopagopus schioedtei</i>),146,233
<i>Omothymus thorelli</i> (Simon, 1901)	/	/									/							191, 176 (both as <i>Cyriopagopus thorelli</i>),146,233
<i>Omothymus violaceopes</i> (Abraham, 1924)	/	/									/							2, 133 (both as <i>Lampropelma violaceopes</i>),,233
<i>Phlogiellus inermis</i> (Aussere, 1871)	/	/																133,146,233
<i>Phlogiellus obscurus</i> (Hirst, 1909)	/		/	/	/													66 (as <i>Selenocosmia obscura</i>), 95, 94,146,233
<i>Phlogiellus pelidnus</i> Nunn, West & von Wirth, 2016	/		/		/													150,,233
<i>Phormingochilus everetti</i> Pocock, 1895	/		/	/	/													94,146,233
<i>Phormingochilus pennellhewlettorum</i> Smith & Jacobi, 2015	/		/	/														196,146,233
<i>Poecilotheria striata</i> Pocock, 1895	/	/									/							133,,233
<i>Psednocnemis jeremyhuffi</i> West & Nunn, 2010	/	/				/					/							229 (as <i>Coremiocnemis jeremyhuffi</i>),146,233
<i>Psednocnemis brachyramosa</i> (West & Nunn 2010)	/	/				/								/				229 (as <i>Coremiocnemis brachyramosa</i>), 230, 170,146,233
<i>Psednocnemis davidgohi</i> West, Nunn & Hogg, 2012	/	/						/										230,146,233
<i>Psednocnemis gnathospina</i> West & Nunn, 2010	/	/				/												229 (as <i>Coremiocnemis gnathospina</i>),146,233
<i>Selenocosmia javanensis</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	/	/																161, 133,146,233
<i>Selenocosmia tahanensis</i> Abraham, 1924	/	/				/												2, 133, 228,146,233
Theridiidae																		
<i>Anelosimus agnar</i> Agnarsson, 2006	/	/												/				4,146,233

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R G	K E K	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Anelosimus kohi</i> Yoshida, 1993	/	/													/				4,146,233
<i>Anelosimus linda</i> Agnarsson & Zhang 2006	/	/				/													4,146,233
<i>Argyrodes argentatus</i> Pickard-Cambridge 1880	/	/						/											147, 246,146,233
<i>Argyrodes fasciatus</i> Thorell, 1892	/																		197,146,233
<i>Argyrodes fissifrons</i> O.P. - Cambridge, 1869	/	/	/		/		/						/						191 (as <i>Argyrodes procrastinans</i>), 197, 94,146,233
<i>Argyrodes flavescens</i> (Pickard-Cambridge 1880)	/	/	/	/	/						/								213 (as <i>Argyrodes sumatranus</i>), 247, 1, 95, 141, 94,146,233
<i>Argyrodes fragilis</i> Thorell 1877	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Argyrodes kualensis</i> Hogg, 1927	/	/											/						67, 133,146,233
<i>Argyrodes miniaceus</i> (Doleschall, 1857)	/	/																	133, 197,146,233
<i>Ariamnes flagellum</i> (Doleschall 1857)	/	/																	133,146,233
<i>Borneoridion spiniferum</i> Deeleman & Wunderlich, 2011	/		/		/														53,,233
<i>Brunepisus selirong</i> Yoshida & Koh 2011	/	/	/	/	/			/											95, 94,146,233
<i>Chikunia bilde</i> Smith, Agnarsson & Grinsted, 2019	/	/				/													196,,233
<i>Chikunia nigra</i> (Pickard-Cambridge 1880)	/	/	/	/	/		/				/								133 (as <i>Theridula caudata</i>), 143, 136,146,233
<i>Chryso urbasae</i> (Tikader, 1970)	/										/								,,233
<i>Coleosoma blandum</i> O.P. Cambridge,1882	/	/													/				133,146,233
<i>Coleosoma octomaculatum</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	/	/						/											138 (as <i>Chryso octomaculata</i>),146,233
<i>Deelemanella borneo</i> Yoshida, 2003	/		/		/														251,,233
<i>Dipoenura fimbriata</i> Simon 1909	/	/	/		/						/				/				96, 94,146,233

Species	M	P	B	S	S	L	P	S	K	P	P	P	K	K	J	M	N	T	References
	A	M	O	W	B	A	H	E	D	E	N	R	E	U	O	E	E	E	
	L		R	K	H	B	G	L	H	R	G	K	L	L	H	L	G	R	
<i>Episinus rhomboidalis</i> (Simon, 1895)	/	/																	133, 197,146,233
<i>Episinus yoshidai</i> Okuma, 1994	/		/		/					/									94,146,233
<i>Faiditus xiphias</i> (Thorell, 1887)	/		/		/														42 (as <i>Argyrodes xiphias</i>),,233
<i>Janula bruneiensis</i> Yoshida & Koh, 2011	/		/		/														94,146,233
<i>Janula bubalis</i> Yoshida and Koh, 2011	/		/		/	/													143, 136, 94,146,233
<i>Janula parva</i> (Wunderlich, 2008)	/	/					/												236 (as <i>Monetoculus parvus</i>),233
<i>Janula triocellata</i> Yoshida and Koh, 2001	/		/		/	/													95, 94,146,233
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> , Koch 1841	/	/						/		/				/		/			138, 135,146,233
<i>Meotipa argyrodiformis</i> (Yaginuma, 1952)	/	/					/								/		/		138 (as <i>Chrysso argyrodiformis</i>),146,233
<i>Meotipa impatiens</i> Deeleman-Reinhold 2009	/	/	/	/	/			/											48, 96, 94,146,233
<i>Meotipa spiniventris</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869)	/	/													/				1 (as <i>Chrysso spiniventris</i>),233
<i>Meotipa thalerorum</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2009	/	/						/											48,146,233
<i>Molione christae</i> Yoshida, 2003	/		/		/														251,233
<i>Molione kinabalu</i> Yoshida, 2003	/		/		/														251, 94,146,233
<i>Molione triacantha</i> Thorell, 1892	/	/					/												234, 133, 197,146,233
<i>Molione uniacantha</i> Wunderlich, 1995	/	/					/												234, 236 133, 94,146,233
<i>Nesticodes rufipes</i> (Lucas 1846)	/	/	/		/			/											22 (as <i>Theridion rufipes</i>), 133, 132, 94,146,233
<i>Nihonhimea mundula</i> (L. Koch 1872)	/	/	/		/		/	/				/							194 (as <i>Theridion mundulum</i> , 42 (as <i>Achaearanea mundula</i>), 143 (as <i>Parasteatoda mundula</i>), 94, 199, 170,146,233
<i>Parasteatoda celsabdomina</i> (Zhu 1998)	/	/									/								138,146,233
<i>Parasteatoda tepidariorum</i> (Koch 1841)	/	/	/		/												/		42 (as <i>Achaearanea tepidariorum</i>), 138, 143,146,233

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R K	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L.Koch, 1875)	/	/										/						138 (as <i>Runcinia albostriata</i>),146,233
<i>Smodicinodes kovaci</i> Ono, 1993	/	/						/										152, 133,146,233
<i>Stephanopsis altifrons</i> Cambridge, 1869	/		/		/													189, 143, 233
<i>Stiphropus ocellatus</i> Thorell, 1887	/	/	/		/		/											94,146,233
<i>Strigoplus albostriatus</i> Simon, 1885	/	/									/							5, 133, 94,146,233
<i>Synema globosum</i> (Fabricius 1775)	/	/									/							138,146,233
<i>Talaus beccarii</i> Benjamin, 2020	/		/		/													19,,233
<i>Talaus nanus</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/	/	/	/		/											50, 19,,233
<i>Talaus triangulifer</i> Simon, 1886	/		/		/													50, 19,,233
<i>Thomisops sanmen</i> Song, Zhang & Zheng, 1992	/		/		/													50,,233
<i>Thomisus callidus</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/	/									/							77,,233
<i>Thomisus guangxicus</i> Song and Zhu 1995	/	/	/		/		/				/							138, 143, 94,146,233
<i>Thomisus perspicillatus</i> (Thorell, 1890)	/		/	/	/													50, 94,146,233
<i>Tmarus loriae</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/	/		/						/							213, 133, 50,146,233
<i>Tmarus orientalis</i> Schenkel 1963	/	/	/		/		/											138, 143,146,233
<i>Xysticus nyingchiensis</i> Song & Zhu 1995	/	/						/										138,146,233
<i>Zametopina calceata</i> Simon, 1909	/		/		/													50,,233
<i>Zygomētis xanthogaster</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	/	/									/							191, 133 (both as <i>Zygomētis cristulata</i>),146,233
Titanoecidae																		
<i>Pandava laminata</i> (Thorell 1878)	/		/	/														95,,233
Trachelidae																		

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R K	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Orthobula bilobata</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/														46,146,233
<i>Utivarachna chamaeleon</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/	/													46, 94,146,233
<i>Utivarachna dusun</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/														46, 94,146,233
<i>Utivarachna fukasawana</i> Kishida, 1940	/		/	/														46, 94,146,233
<i>Utivarachna ichneumon</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/														46, 94,146,233
<i>Utivarachna itiokai</i> Yamasaki, 2023	/		/	/														241, 233
<i>Utivarachna kinabaluensis</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/														46, 94,146,233
<i>Utivarachna phyllicola</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001	/		/	/														46,146,233
Uloboridae																		
<i>Miagrammopes kinabalu</i> Logunov, 2018	/		/	/														116,233
<i>Miagrammopes oblongus</i> Yoshida 1982	/	/	/	/						/								95, 138,146,233
<i>Miagrammopes singaporensis</i> Kulczyński, 1908	/	/								/								77,146,233
<i>Miagrammopes uludusun</i> Logunov, 2018	/		/	/														116,,233
<i>Philoponella quadrituberculata</i> (Thorell, 1892)	/	/	/	/														133, 197, 141,146,233
<i>Philoponella raffrayi</i> (Simon, 1891)	/	/	/	/									/					126, 133, 136,146,233
<i>Philoponella sabah</i> Yoshida, 1992	/		/	/														250,146,233
<i>Uloborus humeralis</i> van Hasselt, 1882	/		/	/														42,233
<i>Uloborus limbatus</i> (Thorell 1895)	/		/	/														95,233
<i>Uloborus oculatus</i> Kulczynski, 1908	/	/																133, 197,146,233

Species	M	P	B	S	S	L	P	S	K	P	P	P	K	K	J	M	N	T	References
	A	M	O	W	B	A	H	E	D	E	N	R	E	U	O	E	E	E	
	L		R	K	H	B	G	L	H	R	G	K	L	L	H	L	G	R	
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas 1846	/	/	/	/	/			/		/									95, 138, 143, 94,146,233
<i>Uloborus spelaeus</i> Bristowe, 1952	/	/						/											22, 133, 132,146,233
<i>Uloborus undulatus indicus</i> Kulczynski, 1908	/																		197,146,233
<i>Uloborus undulatus</i> Thorell, 1878	/																		133, 197,146,233
<i>Zosis geniculata</i> (Olivier, 1789)	/		/		/														213 (as <i>Uloborus geniculatus</i>), 197, 141,146,233
Zodariidae																			
<i>Asceua bifurca</i> B.S.Zhang & F.Zhang, 2018	/		/		/														255,146,233
<i>Asceua curva</i> B.S.Zhang & F.Zhang, 2018	/		/		/														255,146,233
<i>Asceua gruezoi</i> Barrion & Litsinger 1992	/	/						/											138,233
<i>Asceua trimaculata</i> B.S.Zhang & F.Zhang, 2018	/	/					/												255,146,233
<i>Cryptothele sundaica</i> Thorell, 1890	/	/	/	/							/								133, 197, 136, 94,146,233
<i>Heliconilla globularis</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/						/											33,146,233
<i>Heradion damrongi</i> Dankittipakul & Jocque, 2004	/	/									/	/	/						133, 31,146,233
<i>Heradion luctator</i> Dankittipakul & Jocque, 2004	/	/						/			/						/		32,146,233
<i>Heradion pernix</i> Dankittipakul & Jocque, 2004	/	/					/	/			/								32,146,233
<i>Malayozodarion hoiseni</i> Ono & Hashim 2008	/	/					/												153,146,233
<i>Mallinella abnormis</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/													/				33,146,233

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R K	K E L	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Mallinella calautica</i> B. S. Zhang & F. Zhang, 2019	/		/	/															256,146,233
<i>Mallinella comitata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/	/															33,233
<i>Mallinella denticulata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella dolichobilobata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/													/				33,146,233
<i>Mallinella dolichorhyncha</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/								/					/				33,146,233
<i>Mallinella elegans</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/										/							33,146,233
<i>Mallinella elongata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/								/	/								33,146,233
<i>Mallinella fasciata</i> (Kulczyński, 1911)	/	/					/								/				33,146,233
<i>Mallinella flabellata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/	/															33,146,233
<i>Mallinella flabelliformis</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella flagelliformis</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/	/															33,,233
<i>Mallinella gombakensis</i> Ono & Hashim 2008	/	/							/										153,146,233
<i>Mallinella jaegeri</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella laxa</i> B. S. Zhang & F. Zhang, 2019	/	/	/	/													/		256,146,233

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R G	K E K	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Mallinella leptoclada</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/											/	33,146,233
<i>Mallinella longipoda</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/		/														33,,233
<i>Mallinella maruyamai</i> Ono & Hashim 2008	/	/						/											153,146,233
<i>Mallinella microleuca</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella microtheca</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella multicornis</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/									/								33,146,233
<i>Mallinella murphyorum</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/													/				33,146,233
<i>Mallinella obliqua</i> B. S. Zhang & F. Zhang, 2019	/		/		/														256,146,233
<i>Mallinella pectinata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/	/	/			/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella punctata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/		/														33,233
<i>Mallinella robusta</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/								/				33,146,233
<i>Mallinella rolini</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146,233
<i>Mallinella scharffi</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/		/														33,233
<i>Mallinella sciophana</i> (Simon, 1901)	/	/										/							191, 33,146, 233

Species	M A L	P M R	B O R	S W K	S B H	L A B	P H G	S E L	K D H	P E R	P N G	P R K	K E L	K U L	J O H	M E L	N E G	T E R	References
<i>Mallinella simillima</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146, 233
<i>Mallinella sundaica</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146, 233
<i>Mallinella superba</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/		/		/														33, 233
<i>Mallinella tricuspidata</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/												33,146, 233
<i>Mallinella tumidifemoris</i> Ono & Hashim 2008	/	/						/											153,146, 233
<i>Workmania botuliformis</i> Dankittipakul, Jocqué & Singtripop, 2012	/	/					/								/				33,146, 233
<i>Workmania juvenca</i> (Workman, 1896)	/	/	/		/		/								/				33,146, 233

Table 2: *Nomina dubia*

Species	M	P	B	S	S	L	P	S	K	P	P	P	K	K	J	M	N	T	References
	A	M	O	W	B	A	H	E	D	E	N	R	E	U	O	E	E	E	
	L		R	K	H	B	G	L	H	R	G	K	L	L	H	L	G	R	
Corinnidae																			
<i>Sesieutes emancipates</i> Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001												/							46
Lycosidae																			
<i>Hippasa greenalliae</i> (Blackwall, 1867)									/										199
Pisauridae																			
<i>Perenethis unifasciata</i> (Doleschall 1859)																			
Salticidae																			
<i>Euophrys kulczynskii</i> Thorell, 1890											/								133
<i>Maevia persecta</i> Thorell, 1890											/								213
<i>Marpissa elata</i> Thorell 1881		/																	133
<i>Plexippus malayensis</i> Simon, 1864															/				133
<i>Plexippus malayensis</i> Simon, 1864															/				133
Sparassidae																			
<i>Olios annandalei</i> (Simon, 1901)		/																	191
Theraphosidae																			
<i>Cyriopagopus salangensis</i> (Strand, 1907)															/				133 (as <i>Haplopelma salangensis</i>), 145
Theridiidae																			
<i>Theridion labeculosum</i> Workman, 1900		/																	133, 197, 147
Zodariidae																			
<i>Storena obnubila</i> Simon, 1901											/								133 (as <i>Mallinella obnubila</i>)

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